

Degradation of highly chlorinate pesticide, lindane, in water by persulfate activated with ferrioxalate and solar radiation

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Conte, Leandro^{1,2}; Legnettino, Giuseppe¹; Santos, Aurora¹. (1) Department of Chemical Engineering and Materials, Faculty of Chemical Sciences, Complutense University of Madrid, Spain. (2) Instituto de Desarrollo Tecnológico para la Industria Química (INTEC) and, Universidad Nacional del Litoral (UNL), Argentina.

1) photo-reactor, 2) solar simulator), 3) collimator, 4) water filter, 5) filter holder, 6) peristaltic pump, 7) tank, 8) heater, 9) mixer.

The photo-Persulfate degradation of a highly chlorinated aromatic pesticide, gamma hexachlorocyclohexane (γ -HCHs), for conditions of natural pH and using a solar simulator as the radiation source is presented. An experimental design was used to simultaneously evaluate the effect of the main reaction variables: persulfate concentration (PS), iron dosage (Fe), and radiation level (Rad), on γ -HCHs conversion. It was found that the photo-Persulfate process is effective in the degradation of the pesticide employing a solar simulator source when ferrioxalate is used as the catalyst source. Operating the system with high radiation levels, the conversion of γ -HCHs after 6 hs of the reaction was higher than 90 % over the full range of working PS and Fe concentrations.

Introduction

There is significant environmental concern about chlorinated organic compounds (COCs) in wastewater, surface water, and groundwater due to their low biodegradability and high persistence. Under the EU Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC), several COCs (chloroethanes, chlorobenzenes, chlorophenols, dioxins, furans, hexachlorocyclohexanes isomers, etc.) have been added in the last two decades to the list of substances to be monitored, encouraging limiting their production and use. However, due to their extensive use, these COCs still pose a risk for the water quality [1]. Moreover, due to their high toxicity and persistence in the environment, the Environmental Protection Agency has classified HCHs as possible human carcinogens [2].

In this work, gamma hexachlorocyclohexane (γ -HCHs), was selected as a model compound to study its abatement using an innovate photo-Persulfate process at neutral pH conditions using ferrioxalate as catalyst source, which was enhanced with a solar simulator.

An experimental design was carried out to simultaneously evaluate the effect of the main reaction variables: Persulphate concentration (PS), iron dosage (Fe), and radiation level (Rad), on γ -HCHs conversion. The evolution of the chloride concentration in the reactive medium was used as a direct measure of the level of dechlorination of γ -HCHs and its chlorinated intermediates.

Materials and Methods

Experimental studies were performed in a double jacket flat plate reactor of borosilicate glass with

external recycle. The storage tank includes a pH-meter, a thermometer, and a liquid sample valve. A thermostatic bath was used to ensure constant temperature during the reaction and a peristaltic pump to achieve a high recirculation flow rate and good mixing conditions. The total volume of the treated solution was 2.0 L, while the irradiated reactor volume was 0.54 L (See Graphical Abstract).

A solar simulator (Oriel, model 67005) was used as the irradiation source. Here, two systems configurations were studied: (i) Attenuation Filter: Water filter and air mass filter AM1.5 Global; working power, 210W, for low radiation level (Low-Rad) and (ii) Attenuation Filter: Water filter and air mass filter AM1.5 Global, working power, 240 W, for high radiation level (High-Rad). With the selection of these configuration, it is intended to simulate solar radiation levels found in Madrid city, Spain. (40°30' N, 3°40' O, 667 m above sea level). Local radiation fluxes averaged over the reactor window (q_w) were measured with a Flame UV-VIS spectrometer coupled with a monocolin UV-Visible optical fiber ($\lambda_{min} = 300 \text{ nm}$ and $\lambda_{max} = 500 \text{ nm}$). The following values were obtained: $q_w = 9.9 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Ecm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for Low-Rad and $q_w = 1.48 \times 10^{-7} \text{ Ecm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for High-Rad.

To simulate the polluted water, γ -HCHs was spiked in milli-Q water. The water saturation was carried out under controlled temperature ($25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and 24 h of agitation; the γ -HCHs saturation concentration was 9.5 mgL^{-1} . The COCs concentration in reaction samples were identified and quantified by Gas Chromatography with FID and ECD Detectors, using

bicyclohexyl as a standard internal indicator (ISTD). The concentration of PS and Fe were determined by colorimetric titration, using a spectrophotometer at 350 and 510 nm, respectively. Ionic organic by-products, such as carboxylic acids and chlorides, were measured by Ion Chromatography [3]. The collected sample (4mL) was filtered and extracted with 0.8 mL of n-hexane. The mixture of both phases was shaken for 2 min followed by 10 min of settlement, allowing the organic phase separation by decantation. The key process parameters studied were PS (250-1500 mgL^{-1}) and iron concentration (3.5-10 mgL^{-1}), and Radiation level (without, low and high).

Results and Discussion

To avoid iron compounds precipitation and keep them in solution along the photo-Fenton process an oxalate/iron molar ratio of 10:1 was chosen. Under these conditions, the dominant ferrioxalate complex is $Fe^{III}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-}$ (96.25%) (Visual MINTEQ version 3.0, USEPA). This organic complex has higher molar radiation absorption coefficients in the UV-Vis region [4]. In addition, the lindane ($\gamma - C_6H_6Cl_6$) oxidation could generate dechlorinated compounds as short organics acids and eventually carbon dioxide, water, and chlorides (Eq. 1). Thus, the dechlorination degree (Cl^-/Cl_0^-) achieved has been determined by Eq. (2), considering the concentration of chlorides released to the aqueous phase (C_{Cl^-}), and the initial concentration of chlorine ($C_{Cl_0^-}$), calculated from the initial concentration of lindane present.

$$\text{Dechlorination degree } (Cl^-/Cl_0^-) = \frac{C_{Cl^-}}{C_{Cl_0^-}} \quad (2)$$

First, it should be noted that for irradiated

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conditions (High and Low Rad), Lindane conversions higher than 85% are reached after 6 h of reaction (Low-Rad, T=15° C). Being the $X_{\gamma-HCH} = 46.00\%$ in only 0.5 hr of reaction (T=35 °C). Therefore, the efficiency of the innovative photo-Persulfate process proposed is highlighted.

Regarding the level of dechlorination obtained, values greater than 98% are reached in only 3.5 h of reaction using High Rad conditions (T=35°C). However, for Low radiation conditions (T=15 °C) this value is only 75% after 6 h of reaction.

For dark conditions, maximum Lindane conversions of 65% are achieved after only 6 h of reaction (Fe=7 mgL^{-1} , PS= 500 mgL^{-1} , T=35°C). It is worth mentioning that, for none of the dark conditions studied, dechlorination levels higher than 10% are reached after 6.5 h of reaction. Therefore, the significant influence of radiation in the process stands out.

Conclusions

Lindane could be successfully degraded using an innovate photo-Persulfate process. Ferrioxalate and a solar simulator as used iron and radiation source, respectively. Among the studied variables, it could be seen that the largest effect in Lindane conversion was due to Rad (the most significant term).

Keywords: Lindane, Persulfate, Sulphate Radicals, Ferrioxalate, Solar Simulator.

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